

Enhancing Hyperspectral Image Classification with Prototypical Networks and Few-Shot Learning

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Abstract—This research paper presents a novel approach for Hyperspectral image classification using few-shot learning that is based on prototypical networks. Hyperspectral imaging is a technology which captures a huge amount of spectral data. Thus, the traditional machine learning algorithms find it challenging to classify. Few-shot learning is a subfield of machine learning, which classifies new classes with a limited number of examples. This paper uses Prototypical networks as a classifier, which learns the common characteristics of each class by computing the distance between the prototypes and the data that is inputted. The proposed approach was evaluated on a publicly available Hyperspectral image dataset, and the results generated are quite considerable. This study demonstrates the potential of using few-shot learning and prototypical networks in Hyperspectral image classification, which can provide accurate and efficient classification results with a limited number of labelled samples.

Index Terms—Hyperspectral image classification(HSIC), Few-shot learning, Prototypical Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hyperspectral imaging can be described as an emerging technique in remote sensing applications which collects images across a set of narrow adjoining spectral bands to extract high spectral resolution information from the objects and the materials that are being imaged. Hyperspectral image classification can be defined as the process of assigning a label based on its spectral signature to each pixel. As interesting as this task seems it is quite challenging too, due to the high dimensionality of the data and the availability of labeled data being very limited. Few-shot learning [1] is a machine learning technique which aims at drawing out idealistic conclusions from a small set of labeled examples. Prototypical networks are a type of deep learning approach to few-shot learning. Prototypical networks learn a metric space where samples belonging to the same class are grouped together and samples from different classes are far apart. In this research paper, we propose a few-shot learning approach based on prototypical networks for Hyperspectral image classification. Recent advancements in Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning have led to the rise of Deep Learning, significantly improving tasks like classification, object recognition, and remote sensing. Deep learning models have been successfully applied to Hyperspectral Image Classification (HSIC) [7], yielding accurate results. However, these models require a

large amount of labeled data for optimal performance. In meta-learning, the deep learning model must be trained with abundant data in the support set, and performance declines when data is limited.

With improvements in deep learning and computing power, deep learning has been widely adopted for HSIC. Many models have been developed, but they often rely on extensive labeled datasets and contain numerous trainable parameters. Since acquiring large labeled datasets for HSIC is challenging, research has focused on developing deep learning models that perform well with fewer labeled samples [8]. To address this, Few-Shot Learning (FSL) has emerged as an effective approach.

This paper employs Prototypical Networks as a classifier for few-shot hyperspectral image classification. Irfan Khan et al. explored essential conditions for classifier selection in meta-learning in their survey "A Literature Survey and Empirical Study of Meta-Learning for Classifier Selection" [3]. A key requirement for machine learning models is the ability to learn from minimal data, which is particularly important in image classification, where obtaining labeled data can be time-consuming and challenging. Few-shot learning techniques have been developed to help the models learn with a limited number of examples. In this regard, one of the most effective approaches is Prototypical Networks.

Prototypical Networks map high-dimensional input data to a low-dimensional feature space in which examples from the same class are closely grouped, and examples of different classes are well-separated, as first proposed by Jake Snell, Kevin Swersky, and Richard Zemel in 2017. This feature space is referred to as the embedding space, enhancing few-shot learning classification performance.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Hyperspectral imaging is an advanced remote sensing technique where images are acquired across hundreds of narrow and contiguous spectral bands. The result is a three-dimensional data cube in which each pixel contains highly detailed spectral information. In many applications, such as agriculture, environmental monitoring, and mineral exploration, HSI is useful because of the rich spectral data that will provide an accurate material identification.

Traditional machine learning-based approaches, such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), Neural Networks, and Random

Forests, have been used for the classification of HSIs. However, most machine learning methods suffer from the high dimensionality of hyperspectral data; further, obtaining large and sufficient labeled samples is not an easy task since data annotation is a labor-intensive procedure.

Deep learning models show great promise in the extraction of complex spatial and spectral features from HSI data. Nevertheless, their performance is heavily dependent on the availability of extensive labeled datasets. In order to alleviate this dependency, few-shot learning techniques have been explored, which intend to achieve accurate classification with only a few labeled samples.

Several FSL approaches have been proposed for HSI classification:

- SSRN: Li et al. put forward the SSRN, which depends on a pre-trained CNN for the extraction of spectral and spatial features. This is an effective way, but this also reduces its adaptability due to dependency on a pre-trained model.
- Generative Adversarial Networks: Liu et al. proposed a GAN-based approach for generating additional samples to raise the accuracy of a model on few-shot learning. This however requires a large amount of unlabeled samples and often runs the risk of overfitting introduced by the synthetic data generation.

BiLSTM introduced by Niu et al. model both past and future spectral contexts. The performance of this approach would rely on the quality of CNNs pre-trained for feature extraction; hence, it is prone to overfitting when the training data is limited.

- Attention Mechanism: Chen et al. integrated attention mechanisms into their model by incorporating CNNs with attention-based FSL modules. While it showed promises, the levels of susceptibility to overfitting and achieved average accuracy levels.

- Local Receptive Field Expansion: Zhang et al. propose a new approach that expanded the local receptive fields at the stage of few-shot learning to enhance feature representations. Although this achieved great accuracy, it assumes similar distributions between labeled and unlabeled samples for each class - which may not always be true.

These studies demonstrate the potential of FSL in HSI classification while underlining some of the challenges: overfitting, dependency on a pre-trained model, and assumptions concerning data distributions.

In recent times, meta-learning frameworks have become popular for FSL, most of which rely on the Euclidean distance metric. The meta-learning framework typically involves two phases of learning: meta-training and meta-testing. During meta-training, a model learns from a set of related tasks-known as the support set-with the aim of generalizing across tasks. In the meta-testing stage, the model is tested on new, unseen tasks, known as the query set.

Fig. 1. Meta-learning framework illustrating support and query sets.

Fig. 2. Euclidean distance metric used in prototype-based classification.

In that respect, the similarity between new tasks and learned prototypes is measured by the Euclidean distance metric. Based on this distance, the model parameters are updated to allow for accurate predictions on new classes. The performance of the classification is commonly evaluated by cross-entropy loss functions, which effectively quantify discrepancies between predicted and true probabilities.

III DATASET

The proposed algorithm was first tested on the Omniglot dataset, a benchmark for few-shot learning problems. Omniglot consists of 1,623 classes of handwritten characters from 50 various alphabets. Each of these classes was drawn by 20 individuals. We follow the Vinyals et al. protocol that resizes grayscale images to size 28×28 pixels. To increase the number of classes through data augmentation, rotation of the characters in 90° increments was performed.

For training, they used a mix of 1,200 characters and their rotations, totaling 4,800 classes. For testing, the remaining classes and their rotations were left. The embedding architecture had four convolutional blocks, each of which had a 3×3 convolution of 64 filters, followed by batch normalization, ReLU activation, and 2×2 max-pooling. This setup produced a 64-dimensional output space for the 28×28 input images.

Both the query samples and support samples were embedded using the same encoder at the embedding stage. The meta-model was optimized with the Adam optimizer along

with Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) to train the meta-model. Prototypical networks were trained using the Euclidean distance measure and had 60 classes and 5 query samples per class in each training episode.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAM

Fig. 3. Framework of Training Phase

Fig. 4. Classification in the Testing Phase

B. FUNCTIONAL MODULES

The task of "Hyperspectral image classification using few-shot learning" has been performed using meta-learning as its backdrop. Various functional modules have been incorporated into the meta-model.

- 1) Meta-learning module
- 2) Data Augmentation
- 3) Classifier module
- 4) Feature Extractor module
- 5) Distance metric module
- 6) Loss function and optimizer module
- 7) Datasets Module

1) *Meta-learning Module:* Meta-learning or "learning to learn" is a branch of machine learning dedicated to creating ML algorithms that are capable of "learning how to learn." Meta-learning's chief objective is reducing data usage through experience gained, creating models with the ability to learn new tasks efficiently. There are two steps involved in the meta-learning algorithm: meta-training and meta-testing. In meta-learning, the training set is known as the support set, and the test set is termed the query set.

Few-shot learning can generally be represented as an N -way k -shot problem where N refers to the number of classes in each training task support set, and k refers to the number of samples in each class. Typically, k does not exceed 20.

Fig. 5. Meta-learning Process

The below figure gives a brief overview of the meta-learning process.

Fig. 6. Meta-learning Overview

During the meta-training stage, the meta-model is trained on a set of related tasks, such as classification, regression, or other similar tasks. The goal is to learn a meta-model that can generalize across the set of tasks. In the second stage, meta-testing, the meta-model is evaluated on a new task that it has never been trained on before. The Euclidean distance between the new task and the training tasks is computed, and the meta-model is updated based on this distance. The updated meta-model is then used to predict the output of the new task.

2) *Data Augmentation Module:* Data Augmentation has been used to address the problem of limited samples by generating additional samples for few-shot learning. Various random transformations such as rotation, scaling, and shearing have been applied to the original examples for data augmentation, generating new examples used for training the prototypical network.

The following augmentations have been applied:

- **Rotation:** The original image is rotated by a random angle between 0 and 360 degrees, including multiples of 90 degrees.
- **Scaling:** A scaling factor between 0.9 and 1.1 is applied to the original image.

- **Shearing:** A shearing factor between -0.3 and 0.3 is applied.
- **Translation:** A translation factor between -4 and 4 is applied for horizontal and vertical translations.
- **Flipping:** A probability factor of 0.5 is used for flipping the original image.

3) *Classifier Module:* Prototypical Networks have been used as a classifier. Prototypical Networks are a type of deep neural network architecture proposed by Jake Snell, Kevin Swersky, and Richard Zemel in 2017. The central idea is to encode input data into a low-dimensional feature space in which instances belonging to the same class lie close to each other and instances of different classes lie far from each other. Such a feature space is referred to as the embedding space.

Mathematically, prototypical networks can be described as:

$$f(x) = g_{\theta}(x)$$

where g_{θ} is a deep neural network parameterized by θ .

$$c = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i g_{\theta}(x_i)$$

where x_i belongs to class c and N is the number of examples in class c .

Feature representations of the labeled examples in each class are taken by the prototypical layer, which computes the prototypic representation for that task. A prototype is defined as the mean of feature representations of all labeled examples of a particular class.

Fig. 7. Prototypical Networks

In the above graph, P_1, P_2, P_3 are the prototypes (centers) of each class. Class prototypes c_1, c_2, c_3 are calculated from each class's support set (colored circles). Prototypes define decision boundaries using the Euclidean distance metric. A query example x belongs to class 2, as its features (white circle) are within that class's decision region.

4) *Feature Extractor Module:* ResNet-18 has been used as the backbone for feature extraction. ResNet-18 is a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture pretrained on the ImageNet dataset. The feature extractor's purpose is to learn high-level features and extract meaningful, discriminative features for classification.

ResNet-18 has the following advantages:

- Reduces the time required for training the model from scratch.
- Leverages prior knowledge gained from being pretrained on the ImageNet dataset, improving classification accuracy.

5) *Distance Metric Module:* Euclidean distance has been used as the distance metric for measuring similarity between each pixel in the image and the reference spectra for each class. Pixels are assigned to the class with the closest reference spectrum, which corresponds to the lowest Euclidean distance value. The Euclidean distance metric is effective in high-dimensional feature spaces, especially for few-shot learning tasks.

Euclidean distance can be calculated as:

$$\text{distance}(A, B) = \sqrt{(A_x - B_x)^2 + (A_y - B_y)^2}$$

where A_x and A_y represent the coordinates of pixel A, and B_x and B_y represent the coordinates of pixel B.

Fig. 8. Euclidean Metric

6) *Loss Function and Optimizer Module:* The Cross-Entropy loss function has been used as the loss function, and Adam has been used as the optimizer. The Cross-Entropy loss function measures the difference between the predicted and true probability distributions of class labels. In few-shot learning, the true probability distribution represents the true class label.

The Adam optimizer, which combines the advantages of momentum-based optimization and adaptive learning rate methods, is widely used in deep learning for its efficiency and minimal hyperparameter tuning. The combination of the cross-entropy loss function and the Adam optimizer ensures effective training of deep neural networks for classification tasks.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This paper leverages a meta-learning approach grounded in the Euclidean distance metric. Meta-learning [2], or "learning to learn," is a branch of machine learning primarily concerned with building ML algorithms capable of "learning how to learn." The central objective of meta-learning is to reduce data usage by maximizing prior experience consideration in order to create models that can rapidly adapt to new tasks.

The main reason for the meta-learning framework is the various advantages that it has, coupled with its inherent difference from traditional ways of learning. Traditional deep learning frameworks are mostly about training a model to classify objects based on a provided set of training data. The models are then tested on distinct test data once trained, to gauge performance and accuracy. Interestingly, in this process, every class in the training set can comprise many images. What distinguishes meta-learning from traditional learning is the contrast in terms of class composition between the test and train sets. While in traditional learning both sets comprise the same classes, meta-learning provides contrast in class composition between the two sets. But not in the case of meta-learning. The meta-learning algorithm exploited in this paper and the Euclidean distance metric generally encompasses two phases: meta-training and meta-testing. In meta-learning the training set is referred to as the support set and the test set as

the query set. Few-shot learning can in general be exemplified as an N-way k-shot problem such that N stands for the size of the class within every support set used during training and k stands for samples within every class. 'k' under normal circumstances doesn't surpass 20(Figure 2).

In the meta training phase, the meta-model is learned on a sequence of related tasks, e.g., classification, regression or some other related tasks. The training phase aims to acquire a meta-model that has the capacity to generalize over the sequence of related tasks. In the second phase, i.e., the meta testing phase, the meta-model will be tested on a novel task in each training run. This work is referred to as "new" since never before has the meta model ever been trained for this work previously during the stage of meta training. The distance in Euclidean between the new work and train work is calculated, and from this distance, the meta-model is updated. The updated meta-model is thereafter employed to forecast the output of the new work.

The Euclidean distance metric is used generally to estimate the dissimilarity between a learned task and a novel task that predicts output. Bobo Xi et al. [4] first proposed the application of class covariance metric in their algorithm in the area of few-shot learning. The simplicity of applying the Euclidean

distance metric is one of its benefits in the application of meta-learning. Using this metric, it is easier to pinpoint tasks that most closely match the new task, thus offering great insights into its nature. In addition, Euclidean distance metric helps in identifying the most appropriate features of the training tasks, hence efficient feature selection in the new task. In classification tasks, a loss function is utilized to measure model performance on the query set utilizing knowledge acquired in the support image set. As the network gets trained on one task after another, it is able to separate among different classes of data more broadly, in contrast to dealing with a distinct subset of classes. To compute the total loss, the cross-entropy function is used as the selected loss function. The cross-entropy loss function is commonly applied in deep learning for classification tasks because it is universal in application. It is best at determining the difference between predicted probabilities and true probabilities. As such, it is one of the most popular and best options for both binary and multi-class classification tasks, and thus is a natural fit for such cases.

Mathematically, prototypical networks can be described using the below-given formulas

A. Embedding

The embedding function is given by:

$$f(x) = g_{\theta}(x) \quad (1)$$

where g_{θ} is a deep neural network parameterized by theta.

B. Prototyping

$$c = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i g_{\theta}(x_i) \quad (2)$$

N

where x_i belongs to class c and N is the number of examples in class c .

Computation of the distance can be done using:

$$D(x, c) = \|f(x) - c\| \quad (3)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ represents the Euclidean distance.

Softmax classification is performed using:

$$P(y = c|x) = \frac{\exp(-D(x, c))}{\sum_i \exp(-D(x, i))} \quad (4)$$

where i indexes over all classes and y is the predicted class label.

HSIC can precisely be defined as the process of assigning labels to each pixel in the image, by taking into consideration its spectral signature. One of the common strategies for classifying Hyperspectral images can be by using a distance metric to compare the spectral signature of each pixel to a set of reference spectra for each desired class. Euclidean distance is the most used metric when a classification task is taken up.

In this paper, HSIC is being carried out by calculating the Euclidean distance between them using the below-mentioned formula

$$\text{distance}(A, B) = \sqrt{(A_x - B_x)^2 + (A_y - B_y)^2} \quad (5)$$

Here, A_x and A_y represents x and y coordinates of pixel A , while B_x and B_y represent the x and y coordinates of pixel B . The square of the differences between these coordinates is added together, and the square root of the result thus obtained puts forth the value for Euclidean distance between the two pixels.

When using HSIC, this formula can be used for calculation of the Euclidean distance between a pixel in the image and the reference spectra of each class. Therefore, by comparing the Euclidean distances calculated, each pixel is classified into the class that has the closest reference spectrum, with the smallest Euclidean distance value. This formula is applied to each pixel, iteratively repeating the process across the whole image. Therefore, a classification map is produced, tagging each pixel based on its spectral signature.

TABLE I
META-LEARNING

No of Classes	5	5	5	5	5
No of Images per Class in Support Set	5	5	5	5	5
No of Images per Class in Query Set	10	10	10	10	10
No of Training Episodes	2000	4000	6000	20000	40000
Accuracy (%)	95.24	96.54	97.08	97.72	98.46

Fig. 9. Classification map obtained from the algorithm

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accuracy for each class:
Class 0: 86.49 +- 0.00
Class 1: 75.05 +- 0.00
Class 2: 68.91 +- 0.00
Class 3: 93.36 +- 0.00
Class 4: 99.78 +- 0.00
Class 5: 79.60 +- 0.00
Class 6: 88.08 +- 0.00
Class 7: 68.78 +- 0.00
Class 8: 99.89 +- 0.00

```

Fig. 10. Accuracy results obtained on Pavia University

The above figure 10 is a snippet that describes the results thus obtained from the execution of proposed algorithm on the hyperspectral image dataset, the Pavia University dataset.

Pavia University dataset

Pavia University dataset is a remote sensing dataset which consists of Hyperspectral images that are captured by the Reflective Optics System Imaging Spectrometer (ROSIS) sensor. The dataset was collected over the Pavia University campus in Italy. It contains 610 by 340 pixels with a total of 103 spectral bands in the range of 0.43 to 0.86 micrometres.

The dataset can be classified into nine land cover classes, the asphalt, meadows, trees, gravel, bitumen, bricks, shadows, bare soil, and metal sheets

V. CONCLUSION

Hyperspectral imaging captures data in many narrow and contiguous spectral bands, resulting in many bands with high spectral resolution. As the images are of higher dimensions, they require a large number of samples for the task of meta-training. A few-shot learning algorithm, which uses prototypical networks as a classifier with ResNet18 as a backbone for feature extraction, has been proposed. This algorithm classifies the required hyperspectral images into different classes by taking in a limited number of samples. Euclidean distance metric has been used for calculating the distance between the original class pixels and predicted pixels. We conclude that this approach has achieved better accuracy than many other few-shot learning models for the task of hyperspectral image classification.

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

From the implementation of the proposed algorithm, it can be observed that there are several potential applications and a lot of future scope. Below is a list of possible extensions that can be implemented:

- **Application-Specific Studies:** Applying the algorithm to specific applications in hyperspectral image analysis, such as agriculture, environmental monitoring, or mineral exploration.
- **Distance Metric:** Investigating the results by using the algorithm with other distance metrics such as class-covariance metric, cosine metric.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Song, T. Wang, P. Cai, S. Mondal, and J. Sahoo, "A Comprehensive Survey of Few-shot Learning: Evolution, Applications, Challenges, and Opportunities," *ACM Computing Surveys*, 2023. DOI: 10.1145/3582688.
- [2] T. Hospedales, A. Antoniou, P. Micaelli, and A. Storkey, "Meta-Learning in Neural Networks: A Survey," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis & Machine Intelligence*, vol. 44, no. 09, pp. 5149-5169, 2022. DOI: 10.1109/TPAMI.2021.3079209.
- [3] I. Khan, X. Zhang, M. Rehman, and R. Ali, "A Literature Survey and Empirical Study of Meta-Learning for Classifier Selection," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 10262-10281, 2020. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2964726.
- [4] B. Xi, J. Li, Y. Li, R. Song, D. Hong, and J. Chanussot, "Few-Shot Learning With Class-Covariance Metric for Hyperspectral Image Classification," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 31, pp. 5079-5092, 2022. DOI: 10.1109/TIP.2022.3192712.
- [5] M. Ren et al., "Meta-Learning for Semi-Supervised Few-Shot Classification," *ArXiv*, 2018.
- [6] M. Ahmad et al., "Hyperspectral Image Classification—Traditional to Deep Models: A Survey for Future Prospects," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, vol. 15, pp. 968-999, 2022. DOI: 10.1109/JSTARS.2021.3133021.
- [7] S. Li, W. Song, L. Fang, Y. Chen, P. Ghamisi, and J. A. Benediktsson, "Deep Learning for Hyperspectral Image Classification: An Overview," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 57, no. 9, pp. 6690-6709, Sept. 2019. DOI: 10.1109/TGRS.2019.2907932.
- [8] S. Jia et al., "A Survey: Deep Learning for Hyperspectral Image Classification with Few Labeled Samples," *ArXiv*, 2021.
- [9] B. Liu et al., "Deep Few-Shot Learning for Hyperspectral Image Classification," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 2290-2304, 2018.
- [10] W. Wang, S. Dou, Z. Jiang, and L. Sun, "A Fast Dense Spectral-Spatial Convolution Network Framework for Hyperspectral Images Classification," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 10, no. 7, p. 1068, Jul. 2018.
- [11] Yaqing Wang, Quanming Yao, James T. Kwok, and Lionel M. Ni. 2020. Generalizing from a few examples: A survey on few-shot learning. *ACM Comput. Surv.* 53, 3 (2020), 1–34.
- [12] Jun Shu, Zongben Xu, and Deyu Meng. 2018. Small sample learning in big data era. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1808.04572* (2018).
- [13] Biqi Wang, Yang Xu, Zebin Wu, Tianming Zhan, and Zhihui Wei. 2022. Spatial-spectral local domain adaption for cross domain few shot hyperspectral images classification. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.* 60 (2022), 1–15. DOI:
- [14] Yutai Hou, Xinghao Wang, Cheng Chen, Bohan Li, Wanxiang Che, and Zhigang Chen. 2022. FewJoint: Few-shot learning for joint dialogue understanding. *Int. J. Mach. Learn. Cyber.* (2022)
- [15] Gongjie Zhang, Zhipeng Luo, Kaiwen Cui, Shijian Lu, and Eric P. Xing. 2022. Meta-DETR: Image-level few-shot detection with inter-class correlation exploitation. *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.* (2022). DOI:
- [16] Meng Cheng, Hanli Wang, and Yu Long. 2021. Meta-learning based incremental few-shot object detection. *IEEE Trans. Circ. Syst. Vid. Technol.* (2021).
- [17] S. Ravi and H. Larochelle, "Optimization as a model for few-shot learning", *Proc. Int. Conf. Learn. Representations*, 2016.
- [18] Y. Wang, Q. Yao, J. T. Kwok, and L. M. Ni, "Generalizing from a few examples: A survey on few-shot learning," *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 1–34, 2020.